

PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS AFFECTING MEMORY EFFICIENCY IN ADOLESCENTS

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Annotations: *The first adolescence is a negative effect on teenage stress in the process of self-sufficiency, because the data during the study process is abstraction. In addition, teens pursue emotional autonomy during this period. That is, he prefers to walk in the world of imagination, giving in to his imagination, dreams. In this article, today the factors affecting the effectiveness of memory in teenagers and recommendations were provided to prevent them.*

Keywords: *Improving memory, emotions, imagination, memory efficiency, educational activities, adolescence.*

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“In high schools, children are a person and are formed as a team. At the same time, they should not be separated from the environment they have learned. These young people can adversely affect the psyche, their attitude, and eventually education. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure continuity of the educational process, training programs.”

Shavkat Mirziyoyev

It is known that today Uzbekistan has become a youth country. We are witnessing that we are witnessing that the policy of our state is also focused on supporting young people. By the head of our state, the youth is to see the youth as our future and today is being created for them today. It is also clear to our opinion that in 2021 it is declared "the Year of Support for Youth and Strengthening Population Health."

"Youth is our future Bunyodaker!" It is stated that young people are being trusted. This, in turn, requires full effective development of necessary knowledge and skills using the opportunities provided from our youth.

The role of knowledge in the possession of knowledge skills is large. However, if we get the information from the external environment, however, if it comes out quickly from our memory, we will not achieve any efficiency in their training. Because memory is the main condition of education, yet the memory itself and mainly grow in the course of education. In addition, the best memory is logical memory. What psychological factors will cause the rise in logical memory?

First, the person's psychic life depends on what direction of social life, that is, what is interested in. The psychological feature of the logical memory is that the person will remember everything that is important, necessary and interesting for him without mentioning everything in this.

Second, the growth of meaning memory depends on the level of knowledge. The knowledge can find a number of different meanings for a new and comprehensive man who

needs to be remembered, and understands the material who wants to remember a person who can think.

Third, In memory, it is one of the most important conditions for the growth of covenant memory. It is necessary to achieve the knowledge system, not to collect the facts much. When a memory is, the material in memory is accustomed to learning the material that should be left with the plan is accustomed to the plan. [1]

If we have spoken separately for the definition of the memory: **Memory** refers to the psychological processes of acquiring, storing, retaining, and later retrieving information. There are three major processes involved in memory: encoding, storage, and retrieval. Human memory involves the ability to both preserve and recover information. However, this is not a flawless process. [2].

The first adolescence is due to the absence of information in the course of the adultery, causing the abstracts of the first adolia season. In addition, teens pursue emotional autonomy during this period. That is, they prefer to walk in the hopes of their dreams, dreams, hopes of dreams. Due to the fact that at the course process or other times, the memory decrease is clearly visible during adolescence. Because adolescence is due to psychological, physiological, social factors, calculating a heavy complex period.

To increase the productivity of memory:

1. Target determination is because the goal is collected, and the necessary information is stored in your memory.
2. When we are expelling the meaning of the necessary information, we leave a deeper tract in our memory.
3. What is constantly studying is interested in the information given at all when learning accidents in general and we need to learn to appreciate the time.
4. Repeating also develops memory as saying that it is said to be the foundation of knowledge.

In short, there will be no human memory. Because the human memory is muscle. He does not work well until you practice it.

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